

PATRONAGE INDICATORS AND DEVELOPMENT CONSTRAINTS ACROSS TOURIST DESTINATIONS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the indicators of tourist patronage and the constraints to tourism development across selected tourist destinations in Lagos, Nigeria. This study adopted a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques for comprehensive analysis. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select respondents from six categories of tourist destinations: private beaches, public beaches, entertainment and parks, gardens and conservation centers, shopping malls and plazas, and museums and cultural/religious centers. A sample size of 180 tourists was derived based on tourist arrival statistics obtained from the Lagos State Ministry of Tourism and destination managers, representing 10% of visitors to selected high-traffic sites. A total of 165 valid questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed. Data collection was carried out through structured questionnaires, while data analysis involved descriptive statistics (frequency and percentages) and inferential tools (chi-square, correlation, and regression analysis). The findings revealed that beauty of scenery (mean = 4.62), attractiveness (4.46), cleanliness (4.27), hospitality (4.19), friendliness (4.16), and quality of food (4.15) are key indicators influencing tourist patronage. These factors highlight the importance of environmental esthetics, service quality, and cultural experiences in shaping tourists' decisions and satisfaction levels. However, the study also identified major constraints to tourism development, including accommodation (mean = 3.79), lack of funding (3.77), poor facilities management and maintenance (3.73), inadequate accessibility (3.72), lack of awareness and publicity (3.72), insecurity (3.70), inadequate facilities (3.65), and poor infrastructure (3.53). Further analysis using regression revealed that the cost of accommodation and inadequate facilities have a statistically significant negative effect on tourist patronage at the 0.05 level, with coefficients of -0.239 and -0.263 respectively. The model explained 16.9% ($R^2 = 0.169$) of the variation in tourist patronage, indicating that other factors also

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contribute to tourists' behavior while constraints significantly influence tourism demand. The study concludes that although Lagos State possesses considerable tourism potential driven by attractive destinations and cultural richness, structural and economic constraints hinder optimal development and patronage. It recommends improved investment in infrastructure, accommodation costs reduction, enhanced marketing strategies, and strengthened policy implementation to boost tourism growth and sustainability.

Introduction

Tourism is undoubtedly the vital driver of socio-economic development, particularly in emerging economies where diversification away from oil dependency is a policy priority. The tourism sector contributes significantly to employment generation, foreign exchange earnings, and infrastructure development globally (World Tourism Organization [UNWTO], 2022). In developing countries such as Nigeria, tourism offers considerable potential for sustainable growth by promoting cultural heritage, fostering local enterprise development, and enhancing regional competitiveness. However, the extent to which these benefits are realized largely depends on tourist patronage patterns and the enabling environment for tourism development. Lagos State, located in southwestern Nigeria, is widely regarded as the country's commercial] and one of Africa's fastest-growing megacities. As a vibrant urban destination, Lagos State boasts a wide array of tourist attractions, including beaches (e.g., Tarkwa Bay and Elegushi Beach), cultural festivals, heritage sites, and recreational centers. The state's strategic coastal location along the Atlantic Ocean, combined with its rich cultural diversity, positions it as a key tourism destination within Nigeria. Despite these advantages, the tourism sector in Lagos State faces several structural and operational challenges that may hinder optimal patronage and sustainable development.

Tourist patronage is a critical determinant of tourism destinations' success and sustainability. It reflects visitors' frequency, preference, and behavioral patterns toward specific attractions or destinations (Kotler, Bowen, & Makens, 2017). Patronage indicators include visitation rates, repeat visits, tourists' satisfaction levels, accessibility, affordability, and the quality of tourist sites' services and facilities. Understanding these indicators is essential for stakeholders as, as it provides insights into tourists' expectations and informs strategic planning and marketing decisions. In the context of Lagos State, where both domestic and international travelers influence tourism demand, identifying key patronage indicators is necessary to enhance destination competitiveness and improve service delivery. Notwithstanding its tourism potential, Lagos State encounters numerous constraints that impede the development of tourism. These constraints range from inadequate infrastructure, poor transportation networks, environmental degradation, and security concerns to weak policy implementation and limited investment in tourism facilities (Adebayo & Iweka, 2014; Ojo, 2019). Furthermore, issues such as traffic congestion, high cost of services, and inconsistent maintenance of tourist sites may negatively affect tourists' experiences and reduce repeat patronage. Addressing these constraints is crucial for unlocking the state's tourism potential and ensuring sustainable development.

Previous studies on tourism in Nigeria have largely focused on the economic contributions of tourism or destination marketing strategies, with limited attention given to the interplay between patronage indicators and developmental constraints within specific urban contexts, such as Lagos State. This gap underscores the need for empirical investigation into how tourists interact with available attractions and barriers that may limit tourism growth. Against this backdrop, this study examines the patronage indicators and development constraints across tourist destinations in Lagos, Nigeria. Where the objectives are as follows::

- i. ascertain the patronage of tourist sites by respondents in the study area
- ii. Determine tourism development constraints in the study area.

Literature Review

Tourism has been recognized as a critical sector for economic diversification and sustainable development, particularly in developing economies. Recent studies emphasize that tourism significantly contributes to employment generation, foreign exchange earnings, and infrastructure development. For instance, a recent study on tourism and socio-economic development in Lagos State found that tourism plays a vital role in enhancing local economies and improving livelihoods through revenue generation and job creation (Olonade et al., 2025). Globally, tourism has experienced a strong recovery following the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, with international arrivals rebounding significantly by 2024. This recovery underscores the sector's resilience and highlights the importance of improving destination competitiveness and tourist experiences to sustain growth. However, in Nigeria, the level of tourism development remains below its potential due to persistent structural challenges.

Tourist patronage refers to the frequency and pattern of tourists' visits to destinations, including their engagement, satisfaction, and repeat visitation behavior. Recent empirical studies have shown that multiple factors, such as destination attractiveness, service quality, accessibility, and perceived value, influence tourist patronage. Solanke and Dawodu (2023) revealed that tourists in Lagos are primarily motivated by relaxation, sightseeing, and recreational activities, with over half of respondents visiting tourist destinations for leisure purposes. The study further indicated that safety, cleanliness, and service quality are critical determinants of tourist visitation decisions. Similarly, a 2023 study on tourism patronage in Jos Wildlife Park found fluctuations in tourist visits over time, highlighting patronage's dynamic nature and its sensitivity to environmental and managerial factors (Fidelis et al., 2023). This finding shows that tourist patronage is not static but responds to both internal destination factors and external socio-economic conditions.

Recent literature has identified several measurable indicators of tourist patronage that are crucial for assessing destination performance. Tourist motivation remains a key patronage indicator. Studies have shown that leisure, education, research, and sightseeing are the dominant reasons for visiting tourist sites in Nigeria. These motivations directly influence visitation patterns and frequency (Solanke & Dawodu, 2023). Tourist satisfaction is a widely recognized predictor of repeat visitation and destination loyalty. A 2024 study on travel modes in Lagos State revealed that tourists' overall experience and willingness to revisit destinations are significantly influenced by satisfaction with transportation services. This shows that service quality across the tourism value chain is essential for patronage sustainability. In recent studies, accessibility has emerged as a critical determinant of tourist patronage. Research conducted on Freedom Park in Lagos (2024) showed that road transportation plays a vital role in facilitating tourist movement and enhancing visitation rates. Efficient transport systems reduce travel time and improve the overall experience of tourists. Tourist arrival statistics are commonly used as patronage indicators. Lagos State recorded an increase in international tourist arrivals from 14,357 in 2022 to 18,273 in 2024, indicating a gradual improvement in tourism demand. This upward trend reflects the growing interest in Lagos as a tourism destination, although the numbers remain modest compared to global standards. Service quality, safety, and environmental conditions are also key patronage indicators. Tourists tend to favor destinations that offer clean environments, reliable services, and secure surroundings. These factors significantly influence both initial visitation and repeat patronage (Solanke & Dawodu, 2023). Despite its potential, tourism development in Nigeria faces numerous constraints that limit its growth and sustainability. Recent research has shown that macroeconomic factors such as inflation negatively affect

tourism development. A 2024 study found that rising inflation in Nigeria reduces tourist arrivals and tourism revenue, thereby hindering sectoral growth (Raifu & Afolabi, 2024). The high costs of goods and services discourage both domestic and international tourists. Infrastructure remains one of the most significant challenges facing tourism development. Poor road networks, inadequate transportation systems, and unreliable utilities reduce tourist site accessibility and diminish visitor experiences. Studies conducted in Lagos and other Nigerian states consistently highlight infrastructure gaps as major barriers to tourism growth (Salisu et al., 2024; Olawuyi & Onifade, 2024). Transportation inefficiencies, including traffic congestion and limited public transportation options, negatively affect tourist mobility. Although road transportation is widely used, challenges, such as delays and congestion, can discourage tourists from visiting certain destinations. Security concerns remain a critical constraint to tourism development in Nigeria. Perceived insecurity discourages tourist inflow and reduces destination competitiveness. Therefore, ensuring safety is essential for attracting both domestic and international visitors. In addition, weak institutional frameworks and poor policy implementation continue to hinder tourism development. Ineffective coordination among stakeholders, inadequate funding, and lack of strategic planning limit the sector's growth potential. Environmental degradation, waste management issues, and urban congestion also affect tourism development, particularly in urban destinations such as Lagos. These challenges reduce the esthetic appeal of tourist sites and negatively impact the experiences of tourists.

Recent studies indicate a strong relationship between tourist patronage indicators and the constraints affecting tourism development. Tourist satisfaction, accessibility, and service quality consistently emerge as key patronage drivers, while infrastructure deficiencies, economic instability, and security concerns remain major barriers. Lagos State-specific studies highlight the importance of transportation systems, service quality, and safety in shaping tourist behavior. Simultaneously, macroeconomic factors such as inflation and operational challenges within the tourism sector continue to limit growth. Although recent studies have provided valuable insights into tourism patronage and development constraints in Nigeria, integrated analyses that simultaneously examine both variables within a single framework, particularly in Lagos State, are lacking. Most studies focus either on patronage determinants or on tourism development challenges without establishing a comprehensive relationship between the two.

Therefore, this study seeks to bridge this gap by providing a holistic analysis of patronage indicators and development constraints across tourist destinations in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Lagos, sometimes referred to as Lagos State to distinguish it from the Lagos Metropolitan Area, is a state located in Nigeria's south-western geopolitical zone. The study population comprised tourists in the selected study area. Multi-stage sampling procedures were used to select respondents according to the most visited areas in Lagos State's mainland and island and local government areas. This procedure involved the use of tourist arrival statistics obtained during the field survey at the Lagos State Ministry of Tourism and Inter-Governmental Relations and destinations managers. The desk record officer reported gave the average number of tourists visiting the selected sites per day and monthly. Approximately 50,895 people visited selected tourist destinations weekly in 2025.

Based on the data, customers visiting different destinations are categorized according to the segments of the most visited places in Lagos, like: Private & public beaches, entertainment and parks, gardens and conservation centers, shopping malls and plazas, museums, and cultural and religious centers. Multi-stage sampling techniques were used to select sample for the study area. Lagos State has six tourist categories: private beaches, public beaches, entertainment and park, gardens and conservation centers, shopping malls and plazas, museums, and cultural and religious & centers. Based on the high level of patronage, one site from each of the categories

of registered tourist in the selected site was used to draw 10% of the visitors to give a sample size of 180 tourists. 165 questionnaires were retrieved from the tourists. In addition, questionnaires were administered to customers at 30-minute intervals to reduce the chances of giving out more than one questionnaire to a group of tourists visiting together, thereby reducing the level of influence and replication of information/answers. Below are the most trafficked destinations among the same categories.

Table 1: Most Visited by Categories

Tourist Attraction	Patronage average per Month	Sample size
National Museum, Onikan	212	21
Elegushi Beach	342	34
Suntan Beach	404	40
Lekki Conservation Centre	420	42
Freedom Park	204	20
The Palms Mall, Oniru	233	23
Total	1,815	180

Therefore, both quantitative and qualitative methods were used for data collection. Questionnaire administrations were used for the qualitative data, while quantitative data structure interview was used to collect relevant information from the study respondents. Interviews were conducted because of the language proficiency and illiteracy level of the respondents. The collected data were subjected to descriptive statistics (percentage and frequency counts) and inferential statistical tools (chi -square, correlation, and regression) to test the study’s hypotheses.

Analysis and Discussion

The factors that influence respondent’s patronage of tourist sites were beauty of scenery (4.62), attractiveness (4.46), cleanliness (4.27), hospitality (4.19), friendliness (4.16), new impressions and image (4.16), quality and variety of foods (4.15), cultural events/festivals (4.13), safety (4.13), hotel’s quality and service (4.07), security (4.07), communication skills of staff (3.97), shopping possibilities (3.95), presence of beaches (3.89), presence of islands (3.84), discotheques and clubs (3.82), prices of accommodation (3.84), quality of roads (3.79) and public transport (3.79). This is in line with the findings of Olugbemi et al. (2020), who indicated that staff hygiene (89.2%), attractive outdoor surroundings (100.0%), and good hotel interior and exterior maintenance (100.0%) were some of the factors responsible for patronage in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Indicator considered by the respondents patronizing the Tourist destinations

Variable	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Average/ neutral	Unsatisfied	Very, unsatisfied	Mean
Beauty of scenery	119 (72.1)	35 (21.2)	8 (4.8)	1 (0.6)	2 (1.2)	4.62
Attractiveness	85 (51.5)	73 (44.2)	5 (3.0)	2 (1.2)	-	4.46
Presence of Islands	57 (34.5)	50 (30.3)	40 (24.2)	11 (6.7)	7 (4.2)	3.84
Presence of Beaches	60 (36.4)	52 (31.5)	37 (22.4)	7 (4.2)	9 (5.5)	3.89
Cleanliness	88 (53.3)	44 (26.7)	25 (15.2)	5 (3.0)	3 (1.8)	4.27
Safety	70 (42.4)	59 (35.8)	26 (15.8)	8 (4.8)	2 (1.2)	4.13
Prices of accommodation	51 (30.9)	62 (37.6)	30 (18.2)	18 (10.9)	4 (2.4)	3.84
Communication skills of staff	69 (41.8)	42 (25.5)	39 (23.6)	10 (6.1)	5 (3.0)	3.97

Quality of roads	48 (29.1)	57 (34.5)	42 (25.5)	13 (7.9)	5 (3.0)	3.79
Public transport	50 (30.3)	55 (33.3)	40 (24.2)	15 (9.1)	5 (3.0)	3.79
Hotel's quality and service	75 (45.5)	44 (26.7)	35 (21.2)	5 (3.0)	6 (3.6)	4.07
Discotheques and clubs	53 (32.1)	56 (33.9)	36 (21.8)	14 (8.5)	6 (3.6)	3.82
Security	69 (41.8)	57 (34.5)	24 (14.5)	11 (6.7)	4 (2.4)	4.07
Hospitality	77 (46.7)	55 (33.3)	21 (12.7)	11 (6.7)	1 (0.6)	4.19
Friendliness	81 (49.1)	45 (27.3)	26 (15.8)	11 (6.7)	2 (1.2)	4.16
Cultural events/festivals	72 (43.6)	53 (32.1)	31 (18.8)	7 (4.2)	2 (1.2)	4.13
Shopping possibilities	57 (34.5)	59 (35.8)	38 (23.0)	5 (3.0)	6 (3.6)	3.95
Quality and variety of foods	82 (49.7)	43 (26.1)	27 (16.4)	9 (5.5)	4 (2.4)	4.15
New impressions and image	83 (50.3)	47 (28.5)	23 (13.9)	3 (1.8)	9 (5.5)	4.16

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Constraints to tourism developments in the study area

Table 2 shows that cost of accommodation (3.79) ranked highest among the constraints to tourism developments in Lagos State. Lack of funding (3.77), poor management and maintenance of facilities (3.73), inadequate/poor accessibility to and/or within destinations (3.72), lack of awareness and publicity (3.72), insecurity (3.70), inadequate facility (3.65) and poor infrastructure (3.53). This is in line with the findings of Odunlami and Ijeomah (2016), who indicated that inadequate funding, inadequate personnel, insecurity, inadequate facilities, dilapidated facilities, lack of accommodation, and lack of conveniences were the challenges of tourism in Lagos destinations as identified tourist respondents.

Table 3: Distribution by constraints to tourism development in the study area

Challenges	Very severe	Severe	Less severe	Not severe	Not a constraint	Mean
Lack of funding	57 (34.5)	56 (33.9)	26 (15.8)	9 (5.5)	17 (10.3)	3.77
Lack of awareness and publicity	54 (32.7)	53 (32.1)	30 (18.2)	14 (8.5)	14 (8.5)	3.72
Poor infrastructure	39 (23.6)	61 (37.0)	31 (18.8)	17 (10.3)	17 (10.3)	3.53
Inadequate/poor accessibility to and/or within destinations	47 (28.5)	62 (37.6)	29 (17.6)	17 (10.3)	10 (6.1)	3.72
Poor management and maintenance of facilities	45 (27.3)	59 (35.8)	40 (24.2)	13 (7.9)	8 (4.8)	3.73
Insecurity	51 (30.9)	56 (33.9)	29 (17.6)	16 (9.7)	13 (7.9)	3.70
Cost of accommodation	54 (32.7)	59 (35.8)	25 (15.2)	17 (10.3)	10 (6.1)	3.79
Inadequate Facility	46 (27.9)	56 (33.9)	35 (21.2)	15 (9.1)	13 (7.9)	3.65

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Relationship between the constraints to tourism developments and the level of customers' patronage of tourism destinations

Table 4 shows the relationship between tourism development constraints and the level of customer patronage of tourism destinations. The results revealed that two constraining factors explained 16.9% (R² = 0.169) of the total variation in the level of patronage of tourism destinations by customers. The regression coefficients of the two significant variables were cost of accommodation (-0.239) and inadequate facility (-0.263) at the 0.05 level

of significance. This indicates that the cost of accommodation and inadequate facilities influenced the level of patronage of tourism destinations by customers.

Table 4: Regression analysis of relationship between constraints to tourism developments and the level of customers’ patronage of tourism destinations

Constraints	Coefficient	Sig
(Constant)	66.306**	0.000
Lack of funding	-0.096	0.310
Lack of awareness	0.067	0.500
Poor infrastructure	-0.102	0.345
Inadequate accessibility	0.064	0.545
Poor management	0.017	0.856
Insecurity	-0.045	0.679
Cost of accommodation	-0.239**	0.017
Inadequate facility	-0.263**	0.011
R ²	0.169	
Adjusted R ²	0.127	
F-statistics	3.972**	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. Source: Field Survey, 2026

Discussion and Findings

The analysis revealed that respondents’ patronage of tourist destinations is largely influenced by the destinations’ experiential and environmental attributes. The most significant indicators were beauty of scenery (mean = 4.62), attractiveness (4.46), cleanliness (4.27), hospitality (4.19), friendliness (4.16), and quality of food (4.15). This finding shows that tourists are more inclined to visit destinations that offer esthetic appeal, pleasant environments, and quality service delivery. The prominence of scenery and attractiveness aligns with contemporary tourism studies, which emphasize the importance of destination image and physical appeal in influencing travel decisions. Cleanliness and safety, which also ranked highly, further reinforce the importance of maintaining hygienic and secure environments for tourists. These factors are critical in shaping tourists’ perceptions and satisfaction, thereby encouraging repeat visitation and positive WOM. Additionally, social and cultural factors such as cultural festivals (4.13) and hospitality significantly contribute to tourist patronage. This highlights the role of cultural heritage and human interaction in enhancing the experiences of tourists. The moderate ratings for infrastructure-related variables, such as road quality (3.79) and public transportation (3.79) indicate that these factors are important but not as influential as experiential attributes. However, their relatively lower scores may signal underlying infrastructural deficiencies that could affect tourism sustainability in the long term

However, the study identified several constraints that hinder tourism development in Lagos State. The most significant constraint was the cost of accommodation (mean = 3.79), followed closely by lack of funding (3.77), poor management and maintenance of facilities (3.73), inadequate accessibility (3.72), lack of awareness and publicity (3.72), insecurity (3.70), inadequate facilities (3.65), and poor infrastructure (3.53). The high ranking of accommodation cost indicates that tourists’ affordability remains a critical issue. High accommodation costs may discourage both domestic and international visitors, reducing overall patronage. Similarly, lack of funding and poor facility management shows that Lagos State’s tourism development suffers from inadequate investment and inefficient resource utilization. Accessibility challenges and poor infrastructure further highlight systemic issues within the tourism sector. Difficulties in reaching tourist destinations, coupled with inadequate

transportation systems, can significantly reduce these sites' attractiveness. Moreover, insecurity remains a persistent concern that affects tourists' confidence and willingness to visit certain destinations. The findings also reveal that a lack of awareness and publicity is a major constraint, indicating that many tourist destinations in Lagos State are not adequately promoted. This limits visibility and reduces potential tourist inflow. These results are consistent with those of previous studies that identified funding, infrastructure, and security challenges as key barriers to tourism development in Nigeria.

The regression analysis revealed that tourism development constraints significantly influence the level of tourist patronage. The model explained 16.9% ($R^2 = 0.169$) of the variation in tourist patronage, indicating that other factors not captured in the model also influence patronage. Notably, the cost of accommodation (-0.239) and inadequate facilities (-0.263) were found to have a statistically significant negative impact on tourist patronage at the 0.05 level. This implies that increases in accommodation costs and inadequate facilities lead to a decline in tourist visits. The negative coefficients of these variables indicating that addressing affordability and improving facilities could significantly enhance tourist patronage. Other variables, such as lack of funding, insecurity, and poor infrastructure, were not statistically significant in the regression model, although they remain important challenges based on descriptive analysis. These findings highlight the critical role of economic and infrastructural factors in determining tourism demand. While esthetic and experiential attributes attract tourists, structural deficiencies can limit their ability to sustain patronage.

Conclusion

This study examined the indicators of tourist patronage and constraints to tourism development in Lagos State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that environmental attractiveness, cleanliness, hospitality, and service quality primarily influence tourist patronage. These factors play a crucial role in shaping the experiences of tourists and determining their likelihood of revisiting destinations. However, the study also identified significant constraints that hinder tourism development, including high accommodation costs, inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, insecurity, and lack of effective promotion. Among these, the cost of accommodation and inadequate facilities had a significant negative impact on tourist patronage. The study concludes that while Lagos State possesses strong tourism potential, the sector's sustainability and growth depend on addressing key structural and economic challenges. Enhancing affordability, improving infrastructure, and strengthening destination management are essential for increasing tourist patronage and achieving sustainable tourism development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Hospitality industry stakeholders should adopt competitive pricing strategies and offer flexible packages to make accommodation more affordable for tourists.
2. Continuous investment in the development and maintenance of tourism facilities is needed.
3. Government and private sector collaboration should be strengthened to increase tourism development funding. Public-private partnerships can be leveraged to finance large-scale tourism projects.
4. Efforts should be made to improve road networks and transportation systems to facilitate easy access to tourist destinations. Efficient transport systems will significantly enhance tourist mobility and satisfaction.
5. To ensure the safety of visitors, adequate security should be provided at tourist destinations. The presence of trained security personnel and surveillance systems will boost the confidence of tourists.
6. Tourism authorities should intensify marketing campaigns to increase tourist destination awareness in Lagos State. Digital marketing platforms and international tourism fairs can promote destinations globally.

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